

Chemical components of *Pongamia pinnata* L.

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Phytochemical study of *Pongamia pinnata* seed coat has resulted in the isolation of two new ketones 8-pentadecanone and 17-tritriacontanone along with the known compounds dotriacontane, 1-hentriacontanol, pongaglabol, karanjin, lanceolatin B and 2'-methoxyfurano[2'', 3''-7,8]flavone.

Pongamia pinnata L. syn. *Derris indica* (Lam.) Bennett (Leguminosae) is distributed throughout India and often cultivated as avenue tree. The plant is known to have very high medicinal value¹. Seeds are anthelmintic, bitter, acrid and carminative². The seed coat/shells of the plant are known to contain flavones³. We have undertaken the reinvestigation of its seed shells and isolated two new ketones along with six known compounds from the methanol extract. Herein, we report the isolation and characterization of these compounds.

Results and discussion

8-Pentadecanone (**1**) was obtained on elution with petroleum ether as colourless solid. The IR spectrum showed the presence of a carbonyl group (1724 cm^{-1}). The GC-MS and elemental analysis suggested the molecular formula to be $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}$. The ^1H NMR spectrum exhibited a triplet at δ 2.32 (4H), which was assigned to two methylenes α to keto group. A multiplet at δ 1.53 (4H), was attributable to two methylenes β to a keto group. A broad signal at δ 1.26 (16H), was assignable to eight methylenes. Another triplet at δ 0.88 (6H), was assigned to two methyl groups. The compound could thus be characterized as 8-pentadecanone (**1**). The MS fragmentation pattern (experimental) also supported the proposed structure **1**.

17-Tritriacontanone (**4**) was obtained on elution with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1) as colourless solid. The IR spectrum exhibited the presence of a carbonyl group (1706 cm^{-1}). The MS and elemental analysis suggested the molecular formula for the compound to be $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{66}\text{O}$. In the ^1H NMR spectrum, a triplet at δ 2.35 (4H), was assignable to two methylenes α to keto group. A multiplet at δ 1.56 (4H), could be two methylenes β to keto group. A broad signal at δ 1.26 (52H), was assignable to twenty-six methylenes. Another triplet at δ 0.88 (6H), was assigned to two methyl

groups. From the above data, the compound was characterized as 17-tritriacontanone (**4**). The MS fragmentation pattern (experimental) supported the assigned structure (**4**).

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined on a Ganson apparatus. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Hitachi 570 spectrophotometer, ^1H NMR spectra (CDCl_3) on Bruker AC-300F (300 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a VG-70S 11-250J GC-MS-DS spectrophotometer.

Seeds of *P. pinnata* were collected from Landscape, Chaudhary Charan Singh Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, Haryana, India.

The dried seed shells (5 kg) of plant were extracted with methanol. The extract was concentrated on a water-bath and the viscous mass thus obtained was subjected to silica gel (60–120 mesh) column chromatography with solvents of increasing polarity.

8-Pentadecanone (1) : It was obtained as a colourless solid (20 mg), m.p. 62° (Found : C, 79.62, H, 13.25. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}$ requires : C, 79.64, H, 13.27%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 723, 802, 922, 1098, 1176, 1413, 1724, 2849, 2919 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 2.32 (4H, t, J 7.0 Hz, $2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CO}$), 1.53 (4H, m, $2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}$), 1.26 (16H, br, $8 \times \text{CH}_2$), 0.88 (6H, t, J 7.0 Hz, $2 \times \text{Me}$); m/z (% abundance) 220 (M- 3H_2 , 3), 211 (3), 205 (22), 183 (3), 177 (2), 155 (7), 149 (30), 141 (9), 135 (3), 111 (37), 97 (60), 71 (100).

Dotriacontane (2) : The compound obtained on elution with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 9) as colourless waxy solid, 10 mg., m.p. 70° (lit⁴. m.p. 69.6°); ν_{max} (KBr) 724, 910, 1021, 1466, 2366, 2849, 2919 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.24 (60H, br, $30 \times \text{CH}_2$), 0.88 (6H, t, J 7.5 Hz, $2 \times \text{Me}$).

1-Hentriacontanol (3) : It was obtained as colourless

solid (on elution with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1), 15 mg, m.p. 87° (lit.⁴ m.p. 87.1–87.2°); ν_{\max} (KBr) 561, 724, 1022, 1466, 2360, 2849, 2918, 3367 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 3.64 (2H, t, J 7.0 Hz, CH_2OH), 1.54 (2H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$), 1.26 (57H, br, $28 \times \text{CH}_2$, OH), 0.88 (3H, t, J 7.0 Hz, $1 \times \text{Me}$); m/z (% abundance) 447 (M+1- 3H_2 , 3), 196 (3), 181 (5), 153 (10), 125 (27), 111 (50), 83 (100).

17-Tritriacontanone (4) : It was obtained as a colourless solid (20 mg), m.p. 67° (Found : C, 82.83; H, 13.78. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{66}\text{O}$ requires : C, 82.84; H, 13.80%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 544, 724, 941, 1298, 1465, 1706, 2360, 2849, 2919 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 2.35 (4H, t, J 7.0 Hz, CH_2CO), 1.56 (4H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}$), 1.26 (52H, br, $26 \times \text{CH}_2$), 0.88 (6H, t, J 7.0 Hz, $2 \times \text{Me}$); m/z (% abundance) 480 (M+2, 11), 438 (16), 424 (43), 410 (14), 409 (6), 396 (23), 381(7), 185 (14), 111 (30), 73 (100).

Pongaglabol (5-hydroxyfuranof[2'',3''-7,8]flavone (5) : It was obtained on elution with benzene, 15 mg, m.p. 198° (lit.⁵ m.p. 198°); ν_{\max} (KBr) 498, 670, 850, 960, 1072, 1352, 1451, 1533, 1664, 2361, 2849, 2917, 3399 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 7.95 (2H, dd, J 7.5 and 2.5 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 7.59 (5H, m, H-6, H-3', H-4', H-5' and H-5''), 7.26 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, H-4''), 6.90 (1H, s, OH), 6.82 (1H, s, H-3); m/z (% abundance) 279 (M+1, 20), 278 (100), 176 (79), 165 (7), 148 (11), 120 (18), 102 (15).

Karanjin (3-methoxyfuranof[2'',3''-7,8]flavone (6) : It was obtained on elution with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 19) and crystallized from benzene, 30 mg, m.p. 157° (lit.⁶ m.p. 158–159°); ν_{\max} (KBr) 590, 795, 956, 1051, 1079, 1285, 1339, 1409, 1624, 2851, 2929 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 8.17 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz, H-5), 8.11 (2H, dd, J 7.5 and 2.5 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 7.70 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, H-5''), 7.52 (4H, m, H-6, H-3', H-4', H-5'), 7.15 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, H-4''), 3.93 (3H, s, OMe); m/z (% abundance) 293 (M⁺+1, 11), 292 (M, 65), 291 (100), 176 (3), 160 (44), 132 (10), 105 (9).

Lanceolatin B (furanof[2'',3''-7,8]flavone (7) : Elution with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 19) afforded this compound, 30 mg, m.p. 137.5° (lit.⁵ m.p. 137°); ν_{\max} (KBr) 466, 628, 896, 918, 961, 1033, 1069, 1112, 1359, 1452, 1492, 1529,

1646, 2361, 2849, 2917 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 8.15 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-5), 7.95 (2H, dd, J 7.5 and 2.5 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 7.76 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, H-5''), 7.56 (4H, m, H-6, H-3', H-4' and H-5'), 7.19 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, H-4''), 6.84 (1H, s, H-3); m/z (% abundance) 261 (M+1, 3), 234 (5), 160 (100), 132 (10), 117 (18), 77 (20).

2'-Methoxyfuranof[2'',3''-7,8]flavone (8) : Elution with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 19) afforded this compound, 20 mg., m.p. 178° (lit.⁷ m.p. 180–181°); ν_{\max} (KBr) 479, 560, 647, 729, 880, 925, 1033, 1111, 1250, 1369, 1480, 1628, 2361, 2837, 2935, 3005 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 7.96 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-5), 7.93 (1H, d, J 9.0 and 2.5 Hz, H-6'), 7.77 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, H-5''), 7.54 (4H, m, H-3', H-4', H-5' and H-6), 7.19 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, H-4''), 6.80 (1H, s, H-3), 3.93 (3H, s, OMe); m/z (% abundance) 292 (M, 100), 190 (49), 176 (3), 162 (17).

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